

UV-WATER WEATHERING DEGRADATION OF THE FLAX FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of weathering aging on the flax fiber reinforced polymer composites for civil engineering applications. The specimens were exposed to an accelerated weathering environment simulating the outdoor environment for up to 1500 hours. Tensile and three-point bending tests were performed to evaluate the mechanical degradation. Microscope observation was employed to check the change of fiber and matrix. All samples experienced reductions in both tensile and flexural properties with increased exposure time. However, the thickness of sample are found to affect the weathering effect, which is the increased thickness can delay the degradation of mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS

Flax fibers; Weathering; Durability

INTRODUCTION

The use of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites in civil engineering is becoming increasingly popular due to their numerous benefits such as lightweight, high strength, and design freedom (Dittenber & Gangarao, 2012). Recently, natural plant fiber has emerged as a sustainable and energy-efficient alternative to synthetic carbon/glass fiber. Natural plant fiber provides better modulus-weight and stress-weight ratios than synthetic fiber, which makes them an appealing option for infrastructure construction engineering (Mohanty et al., 2002). Pilot projects have utilized plant fiber reinforced polymer composites (PFRP) in structures such as pedestrian bridges (Blok et al., 2019), concrete tube strengthening wrappers (Yan & Chouw, 2013), and sandwich panels made of jute fiber reinforced polymer composites (S. Li et al., 2020). However, how well these engineering applications will hold up in the long term is still unclear. More research is necessary to understand the long-term behavior of PFRP in different environmental conditions.

Unlike glass fiber or carbon fiber, natural plant fiber's mechanical performance is severely affected by environmental factors, such as UV irradiation, humidity, and temperature, due to the heterogeneity of its pectin and cellulose composition (M. Li et al., 2020). The long-term durability of PFRP poses a significant challenge to its adoption in the construction industry as the FRP components used outdoors are subjected to various weathering factors, such as rain, high temperatures, and exposure to sunlight (Peng et al., 2014).

Numerous studies have explored the long-term performance of PFRP. Scida et al. (2013) revealed that the modulus and strength of flax/epoxy composites degraded unevenly during hygrothermal aging, with the modulus decreasing by 60%, compared to a 14% reduction in tensile strength. Xu et al. (2023) found that the viscoelastic properties of flax/polyester composites varied significantly depending on the environmental humidity. Wang et al. (X. Wang et al., 2019) discovered that water-immersion aging adversely affected the dynamic and static mechanical properties of flax/epoxy composites. Gassan et al. (2001) reported that the temperature degradation for mechanical properties of jute and flax fiber occurred at approximately 170°C.

Besides moisture, ultraviolet (UV) irradiation is another environmental factor that can cause polymer degradation in PFRP during service. When exposed to UV irradiation, surface oxidation and interfacial degradation are the primary reasons for the mechanical degradation of PFRP (Yan et al., 2015). The photodegradation of composites made from natural fiber and polymers is influenced by several factors, such as fiber content, coupling agents, and weathering conditions (Hallonet et al., 2019).

The effect of weathering on PFRP in the outdoor environment should cover the combined action of UV irradiation, heat, and moisture, which can be accomplished through natural or artificial aging (W. Wang et al., 2005). The degradation of PFRP in the weathering aging process can be evaluated by quantifying chemical degradation or by analyzing physical properties such as mechanical behavior and visual appearance (Benini et al., 2011). Several studies have investigated the effects of weathering on the mechanical properties of PFRP (Yan et al., 2015) (Hallonet et al., 2019) (Nguyen et al., 2012). However, most of these neglected the effect of samples' thickness, and it is rare to find a study about the weathering degradation of PFRP made of flax fiber and polyester.

This study aims to investigate the impact of weathering on the mechanical properties of flax fiber reinforced polymer composites (FFRP), which are commonly used in civil engineering applications. An accelerated weathering program involving UV irradiation, water spraying, and condensation was used to simulate the outdoor weathering environment. The study examined the tensile and flexural properties of the weathered FFRP samples to quantify the extent of mechanical degradation caused by weathering. Additionally, the surface of the exposed samples was checked by the optical microscope, and the change of the fiber-matrix interface was checked by the scanning electron microscope. The results indicate that weathering has a significant effect on the mechanical properties of FFRP, particularly tensile and flexural properties. Moreover, the thickness of the FFRP samples played a significant role in the degree of mechanical degradation caused by weathering. These findings provide valuable insights into the design and maintenance of FFRP structures in civil engineering and inform the development of durability standards for FFRP materials exposed to outdoor environments.

Material and methods

Sample preparation

FFRP sample plates shown in Figure 1(a) were manufactured using vacuum infusion with unsaturated polyester resin and unidirectional flax fiber fabrics. Samples were manufactured in two thicknesses (2 mm and 4 mm) to investigate the influence of the sample's thickness on the weathering degradation. All samples had a fiber volume fraction of approximately 40%. The area density of the unidirectional flax fiber fabrics is 420 g/mm². The flax fabrics were stored in a stable environment of 23°C and 65% relative humidity before manufacturing. The infusion process was carried out under a vacuum bump at a pressure of -1 bar, and the samples were post-cured by heating to 120°C for 12 hours. After post-curing, the samples were stored in a dark room at ambient temperature for two weeks to ensure complete curing.

a) Samples for the experiment

b) QUV machine for weathering exposure

Figure 1: (a) Samples as manufactured and (b) the QUV machine used for weathering exposure

Weathering aging

Samples manufactured were exposed to an accelerated weathering program provided by the QUV testing machine (Figure 1(b)) following ISO 4892-3(2016). The weathering program consists of 8 hours of UV light exposure at 60 °C, followed by 0.25 hours of water spray at 20 °C and 3.75 hours of condensation at 50 °C to simulate the effects of sunlight-induced ultraviolet irradiation, the impact of cold rain on the surface, and the moisture content change within the sample, respectively. The total exposure includes three phases of 500, 1000, and 1500 hours, and there are three sets of identical specimens for different exposure durations. UV exposure was provided by a UVA-340 lamp with an irradiance of $0.76 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ at 340 nm to simulate natural UV radiation.

Monotonic tensile test

Tensile tests were performed on the universal mechanical testing machine following ISO 527-5:2021, with a crosshead speed of 2mm/min. The samples used in the test were 15 mm wide and 250 mm long. An optical sensing system was employed to measure the strain development during the test, which did not require contact with the sample. The measurement area was 100mm along the length. The tests were conducted in an environment with a temperature of approximately 20 °C and a relative humidity of 60%. Five replicates were prepared for each kind of the sample.

Three-point bending test

For the flexural tests, samples with unidirectional fiber were tested in three-point bending mode using the Instron 3128, in accordance with the testing code ISO 14125:1998, with a crosshead speed of 1mm/min. The samples had dimensions of 100 mm × 2 mm, with a support span length of 80 mm and an overhang length of 10 mm on each side. There are five replicates tested for each kind of sample.

Scanning electron microscope

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to analyze the fracture surface morphology of the FFRP samples before and after weathering. Cross-sectional observation of the flax fiber and matrix was made possible by cutting the FFRP samples along the fracture direction. An oblique cut was made at an angle from the direction of the fiber to check the change of flax fiber and the interface between fiber and matrix. High-quality images of the composite fracture surface were captured using secondary electron detection and an acceleration voltage of 10 kV. Before imaging, all samples were sputtered with a thin layer of gold with a thickness of approximately 6 nm.

Results and discussion

Appearance inspection

Figure 2. presents the irradiated surfaces of FFRP samples before and after exposure for different durations. After 500 hours of exposure, the surface color changed significantly, indicating degradation of the matrix and fiber due to the combined effect of UV irradiation and water spray. The color change was not obvious between 500 and 1000 hours of exposure but became pronounced between 1000 and 1500 hours again. Color changes are typically attributed to the formation of hydroxyl groups in the polymer during UV irradiation, which causes the material to turn yellow (Homkhiew et al., 2014) (Stokke & Gardner, 2003). Given that the matrix material is transparent, the thickness of the flax fiber is presumed to affect the degradation rate under weathering aging conditions.

In addition to yellowing, the surface of the samples became rougher with increasing exposure time, possibly due to matrix erosion. Matrix erosion may be caused by a synergistic degradation mechanism in which a thin layer on the matrix surface is chemically modified by UV irradiation, then washed away by water spray and condensation, exposing a new layer on the matrix surface (Batista et al., 2015). Although the edge area of the samples was not directly exposed to UV irradiation and water spray, its color still faded during the aging process, indicating that FFRP samples were affected by aging even without UV irradiation. This phenomenon may be attributed to the moisture cycling effect inside the FFRP, where water molecules flow along the flax fiber due to their hydrophilicity, causing moisture content cycling in the unexposed area and leading to erosion of fiber and resin inside the

FFRP sample. However, unlike the area exposed to UV irradiation, the edge area did not show a yellowing trend.

Figure 2: The surface of the sample weathered for different durations

With increasing exposure time, the boundary between the exposed and unexposed areas of FFRP samples became clearer, indicating that UV irradiation greatly accelerated the degradation rate of the material. Erosion occurring both inside and outside the FFRP due to the combined effect of UV irradiation and water spray may severely damage the integrity of the fiber-matrix structure.

Tensile properties

Table 1 presents the mechanical properties of FFRP samples weathered for different durations and the percentage retention of the samples after weathering. The results indicate that the tensile strength and modulus of FFRP samples decrease with increasing exposure time. Notably, for all exposure durations, 4 mm samples show higher retention in tensile strength and modulus compared to 2 mm samples.

Table 1: Tensile and flexural properties of FFRP samples at different exposure durations

Sample Thickness (mm)	Weathering aging time (h)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)
2 mm	0	264.44 (1)	21.03 (1)	215.17 (1)	13.95 (1)
	500	243.51 (0.92)	17.83 (0.85)	198.29 (0.92)	9.82 (0.70)
	1000	233.72 (0.88)	14.58 (0.70)	178.26 (0.83)	8.77 (0.63)
	1500	217.68 (0.83)	12.97 (0.62)	163.26 (0.76)	6.67 (0.48)
4 mm	0	265.16 (1)	20.92 (1)	216.23 (1)	13.83 (1)
	500	252.81 (0.95)	18.57 (0.89)	196.33 (0.91)	9.73 (0.70)
	1000	243.46 (0.92)	15.89 (0.76)	185.52 (0.86)	9.59 (0.69)
	1500	234.17 (0.89)	15.42 (0.74)	176.33 (0.82)	9.02 (0.65)

The tensile performance of 2 mm and 4 mm samples is further illustrated in Figure 3, where a significant loss in tensile strength is observed during the initial 500-hour exposure period for both sample types. As exposure time increases, the rate of loss in tensile strength gradually decreases. Furthermore, the reduction in tensile strength of 4 mm samples is consistently smaller than that of 2 mm samples for all exposure durations. The tensile modulus of 2 mm and 4 mm samples generally follows a similar decreasing trend as tensile strength (Figure 3(b)). Although the rate of modulus loss decreases with exposure time, the loss of modulus in 2 mm samples is more severe than that in 4 mm samples.

After exposure to UV irradiation and water spray for 1500 hours, the tensile strength of 2 mm and 4 mm samples decreased significantly by 17% and 11%, respectively. The reduction in tensile modulus was 38% and 26% for the 2 mm and 4 mm samples, respectively. These findings indicate that

weathering has a significant detrimental effect on the tensile performance of FFRP. The sharp decline in the tensile performance of 2 mm and 4 mm FFRP samples during the initial 500-hour period of weathering suggests that the weathering aging effect is more pronounced in the early stages. The rate of performance decrease slows down with increasing exposure time.

Figure 3: Tensile properties of FFRP samples after different weathering aging duration

After the initial exposure period (500 hours in this study), the main cause of performance degradation is the degradation of fiber and matrix caused by UV irradiation and moisture. This explains why the tensile performance of 4 mm samples declines more slowly than that of 2 mm samples after the initial exposure period. Although the tensile strength and modulus of FFRP samples decrease over time, the overall trend of the stress-strain curves for different exposure periods remains consistent with that of the unexposed samples, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Tensile stress-strain curves of the FFRP samples

Flexural properties

In Figure 5, the bending characteristics of FFRP samples are shown at different weathering stages. The 2 mm and 4 mm thick samples exhibit similar bending characteristics in the unexposed state, which gradually decrease with increasing exposure time. After 1500 hours of weathering treatment, the strength of the 2 mm and 4 mm samples decreased by 24% and 18%, respectively. During the first 500 hours of weathering, both samples showed a similar decrease in bending strength. However, the decrease in the 4 mm sample became smoother after the initial weathering stage.

The bending modulus of the 2 mm and 4 mm FFRP samples significantly decreased with increasing exposure time. In the first 500 hours, the bending modulus of both samples decreased by approximately 30%. Therefore, the flexural modulus of the 4 mm sample decreased more slowly than that of the 2 mm sample, resulting in a final decrease of 52% and 35% in the flexural modulus of the 2 mm and 4 mm samples, respectively, after 1500 hours.

Figure 5: Flexural properties of FFRP samples after different weathering aging duration

In the bending test, it was observed that all samples failed in the tensile region, and no significant damage was found in the compression region. This indicates that the bending strength of FFRP materials is mainly determined by the tensile ability of the fiber. The decrease in bending strength with increasing weathering time means that the flax fiber is adversely affected by weathering, although this effect decreases with increasing material depth. The bending modulus represents the elastic behavior of the fiber and matrix. The significant decrease in the bending modulus in the initial weathering stage indicates that both the fiber and polymer matrix have undergone degradation. After the initial stage, the bending modulus of the 2 mm sample decreased much faster than that of the 4 mm sample. This can be attributed to limited UV exposure on the polymer and fiber, as the proportion of UV-exposed flax fiber and the polymer is higher in the 2 mm sample than in the 4 mm sample. Therefore, the bending modulus of the thicker sample slightly decreased.

Scanning electron microscope check

The 2 mm thick sample weathered for 1500 hours was examined by the scanning electron microscope, as shown in Figure 6. Compared with the unweathered specimens, the fiber in the 1500-hour weathered specimens exhibited more pores and damage points on the surface, with clear gaps between the fiber. In contrast, the fiber in the unexposed sample remained on a neat surface and was kept tightly together. It is speculated that the pores on the fiber surface were caused by the expansion and contraction cycles resulting from changes in moisture content. Though the ultraviolet irradiation would accelerate this process by damaging the polymer surface, the ultraviolet irradiation does not significantly affect the flax fiber.

Figure 6: Scanning electron microscope image of the FFRP after weathering exposure for (a) 0 hours and (b) 1500 hours

Combining the SEM experimental results here with the previous mechanical performance test results, it is clear that the effects of UV irradiation and moisture on FFRP during the combination of UV and moisture content cycles are different. Although the depth of influence of UV irradiation is limited, this effect seems to cause greater damage than a single change in moisture content. Since structures made of FFRP in outdoor environments will be subject to similar weathering conditions, it is essential to apply coatings to prevent structural damage due to weathering. Once it is confirmed that the coating can be kept away from UV irradiation, UV irradiation can be excluded from the design considerations. However, the moisture content and its cycles in the samples can cause FFRP degradation, which must be considered in the design and manufacturing process.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to enhance the durability database and better understand the effect of weathering on composite materials made of natural plant fiber. The weathering aging process of flax fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester composites used in civil engineering applications was evaluated by simulating accelerated outdoor conditions. The instantaneous mechanical properties and long-term creep behavior of the FFRP samples were studied after various weathering exposure periods, and microstructural changes were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy.

The study concludes that weathering exposure leads to a decline in the mechanical properties of FFRP, with a more significant decrease in the tensile and flexural modulus compared to the tensile and flexural strength. SEM studies attribute FFRP degradation to changes in flax fiber, matrix, and their interface. The thickness of the sample would affect the weathering degradation of the FFRP, which is the mechanical properties of the thicker sample degrades more gently. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into the effect of weathering on FFRP and can provide information for developing more durable natural fiber composites for civil engineering applications.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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